

Effect of organic solvents (methylcellosolve, dimethylsulfoxide, acetonitrile and 1-propanol) on the tryptophan-ninhydrin reaction – A kinetic approach

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Kinetics of the tryptophan-ninhydrin reaction at a constant [Triton X-100] ($=50.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) and pH (=5.0), maintained by $\text{CH}_3\text{COONa}-\text{CH}_3\text{COOH}$, in presence of different organic solvents, i.e. methylcellosolve, dimethylsulfoxide, acetonitrile and 1-propanol, has been studied spectrophotometrically at 40°C. In each case, the pseudo-first-order rate constant increases with increase in the proportion of organic solvent. The catalytic role of solvents has been discussed in terms of increasing the solubility of *Ruhemann's purple* (the product) in the solvents and blocking the side reaction. Other reasons for the catalytic role of solvents have also been discussed.

Preparation of the ninhydrin reagent containing different metal ions, solvents and other organic compounds has been the subject of a large number of investigations¹⁻⁵. Furthermore, the formation of purple-coloured product (known as the *Ruhemann's purple*) depends not only on the [substrate] but also on the medium, temperature and oxygen present in the system. Qualitative information is available on the role of organic solvents^{5,6}, but no kinetic evidence is available to distinguish the role of solvents. We, therefore, decided to study the effect of organic solvents (methylcellosolve, dimethylsulfoxide, acetonitrile and 1-propanol) on the rate of *Ruhemann's purple* formation by the reaction of DL-tryptophan and ninhydrin in presence of TX-100 at 40°C. It is pertinent to mention here that no colour developed at 40°C in the absence of TX-100⁷. The results and probable explanations are described in this article.

Results and discussion

In case of amino acid-ninhydrin reaction, the choice of the best conditions for the kinetic experiments is a crucial problem that we address first. Under the kinetic conditions used herein ([tryptophan] $=5.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, [ninhydrin] $=7.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, pH = 5.0, 40°C), the reaction did not take place in aqueous medium⁷. However, the reaction was very sensitive to

the presence of added TX-100; $50.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ concentration was enough to catalyze the reaction. Therefore, all the kinetic runs were carried out in the presence of TX-100.

In order to confirm that the same coloured product is formed in the absence and presence of organic solvents, a series of absorption spectra were recorded after the completion of the tryptophan-ninhydrin reaction at 40°C in presence of [TX-100] $= 50.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. These results are shown graphically as absorbance-wavelength profiles in Fig. 1. The spectra of mixtures containing the reactants in different solvents exhibited the same maxima as that of a solution of *Ruhemann's purple* in aqueous micellar medium (see, for example, Fig. 1 (curve (b))). The spectra consist of two broad bands with $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 400$ and 570 nm. No variation in λ_{max} in different solvents clearly indicates the product of tryptophan-ninhydrin reaction to be the same as in aqueous micellar medium, i.e. *Ruhemann's purple*^{5,8}. As increased absorbance was observed with increase in the % solvent (v/v), several kinetic runs were carried out at 5–35% (v/v) solvents in order to see the effect of varying contents of organic solvents on the reaction rate. The pseudo-first-order rate constants were found to increase with increase in solvent content % (v/v) (Table 1).

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of the reaction product of tryptophan and ninhydrin in absence of TX-100 (a), $50.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ TX-100 (b), $50.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ TX-100 + 20% (v/v) MC (c), $50.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ TX-100 + 20% (v/v) PrOH (d), $50.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ TX-100 + 20% (v/v) DMSO (e), and $50.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ TX-100 + 20% (v/v) AN (f). *Reaction conditions* : [tryptophan] = $5.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, [ninhydrin] = $7.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, pH = 5.0, temp. = 40°C .

Table 1. Effect of various organic solvents on the pseudo-first-order rate constant for the tryptophan-ninhydrin reaction^a

%Solvent (v/v)	$10^5 k_\psi \text{ (s}^{-1}\text{)}$			
	DMSO	AN	MC	PrOH
0.0	8.31	8.31	8.31	8.31
5.0	9.21	11.51	8.44	8.44
10.0	9.97	9.21	8.44	8.44
15.0	11.51	14.58	9.21	9.21
20.0	16.88	16.88	12.21	13.05
25.0	18.42	18.42	13.81	14.58
30.0	19.16	21.49	16.88	17.65
35.0	24.56	24.56	20.70	19.95

^a[Tryptophan] = $5.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; [ninhydrin] = $7.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; [TX-100] = $50.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; pH = 5.0; temp. = 40°C .

It is well known that the amino acid-ninhydrin reactions proceed through the formation of a Schiff base (unstable for isolation) and a series of reactions, involving different intermediates, up to the formation of *Ruhemann's purple*^{5,8}. It is, therefore, necessary to point out the main steps involved in the mechanism of ninhydrin reaction

before discussing the role of solvents.

Scheme 1

According to Scheme 1, the formation of amine B (as an intermediate) is fast whereas its reactions with H_2O and ninhydrin, respectively, are too slow. Thus, amine B simultaneously participates in two parallel reactions : hydrolysis and condensation. The observed catalytic role of solvents is due to diminished hydrolysis of the amine. The increase in the content of solvents % (v/v) is expected to decrease the content of water, which, in turn decreases the hydrolysis of amine. As a result, the rate of the reaction is increased. Secondly, the solubility of *Ruhemann's purple* is less in water in comparison to organic solvents. Thus, blocking side reaction(s) (mainly hydrolysis) and higher solubility of the product play important roles in presence of organic solvents.

According to Scheme 1, the rate law is written as

$$k_\psi = \frac{k_1 K_h [\text{H}_2\text{O}] + k_2 K_p [\text{H}^+] [\text{ninhydrin}]}{(1 + K_p [\text{ninhydrin}] + K_h [\text{H}_2\text{O}])} \quad (1)$$

In presence of organic solvents and at pH 5.0, as the water content decreases, formation of ammonia is negligible. Therefore, eq. (1) can be written as

$$k_\psi = \frac{k_2 K_p [\text{H}^+] [\text{ninhydrin}]}{(1 + K_p [\text{ninhydrin}] + K_h [\text{H}_2\text{O}])} \quad (2)$$

The derived rate law clearly accounts for the fractional-order dependence on [ninhydrin], and this was found to be so⁷. The positive catalytic effect of organic solvents may also be looked upon from the view point of relative participation of water and organic solvent in acid-base equilibria and hydrogen bonding. It has been established that pH of the medium and $\text{p}K_2$ -values of amino acids are responsible for the rate enhancement of amino acid-ninhydrin reaction in non-aqueous organic solvents and amino acid anions are the reactive species⁹. As the [anion] is negligible in the vicinity of pH 5.0 (the maximum pH for ninhydrin reaction), the neutral form of amino acid is the main reactive species under such type of circumstances¹⁰

In order to confirm the hypothesis presented by Friedman⁹, i.e. rate enhancement being directly related to the pK_2 value of amino acid, results of experiments performed in 65% pH 5 buffer + 35% organic solvent are summarized in Table 2. The observations indicate that pH of the working solution does not show any drastic change in presence of the solvents (Table 2).

Table 2. pH and the observed pseudo-first-order rate constants of the tryptophan-ninhydrin reaction carried out in different solvents (35%, v/v)^a

Reaction medium	pH	k_{app} (s ⁻¹)
Buffer (CH ₃ COOH + CH ₃ COONa)	5.0	8.06
65% pH 5.0 buffer + 35% DMSO	6.08	24.56
65% pH 5.0 buffer + 35% AN	5.89	24.56
65% pH 5.0 buffer + 35% MC	5.58	20.70
65% pH 5.0 buffer + 35% PrOH	5.48	19.95

^a[Tryptophan] = 5.0×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³; [ninhydrin] = 7.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³; [TX-100] = 50.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, temp. = 40°C.

The unique behaviour of the solvents may be explained by the fact that with the solvent volume of water decreasing in a given set of experiments, the rate of hydrolysis decreases. Thus, with the increasing organic solvent content, the oxidative side reaction is progressively blocked. The *Ruhemann's purple* being highly soluble in organic solvents imparts increased intensity.

Experimental

Materials and methods : Ninhydrin (E. Merck, India, 99%), DL-tryptophan (Sisco, India, 99%, B/809205), Triton X-100, TX-100 (Fluka, Switzerland, 99%, Prod. No. 93420), methylcellosolve, MC (s.d. fine Chem. Ltd., India, 99%), dimethylsulfoxide, DMSO (E. Merck, India, 99%), acetonitrile, AN (E. Merck, India, 99.5%), and 1-propanol, PrOH (E. Merck, India, 99%) were used as received. Water was double-distilled (first time from alkaline KMnO₄). pH 5.0 sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer¹¹ was used as the solvent for preparing the stock solutions. The pH of the solutions was measured with

Elico model LI-120 pH-meter fitted with an Elico CH-41 combination electrode.

Kinetic procedure : The kinetic experiments were performed at 40°C under nitrogen atmosphere with pseudo-first-order conditions of [ninhydrin] > [tryptophan]. The reactions were initiated by rapid additions of known amounts of ninhydrin solution, equilibrated at 40°C, to mixtures containing requisite quantity of tryptophan, TX-100 and solvent mixtures. The reaction was followed spectrophotometrically by measuring the absorbance at 570 nm^{5,7}. The pseudo-first-order rate constant (k_{app} , s⁻¹) were calculated from the slopes of $\log (A_{\infty} - A_0 / A_{\infty} - A_t)$ vs t plots (A is the absorbance).

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